

The Life of Severus

By Lampros Alexopoulos, University of Thessaloniki

Entry tags: Christian monasticism, Christianity, Syriac Text, Religious Group, Byzantine, Text, Hagiography, Byzantine text

The "Life of Severus" written by Zacharias Scholasticus (or rhetor, or Zacharias bishop of Mytilene) is a work of significant importance for understanding the cultural and spiritual influences, the history of the Monophysite movement during the fifth and sixth centuries, but also of the student environment of Alexandria and Beirut towards the end of the fifth century. Severus is considered as one of the most important Greek theologians of the sixth century and as the main authority on Christology for the Syrian Orthodox tradition. He was born in Sozopolis, in Pisidia, around 459, probably from a pagan family. He began his studies in Alexandria and then he went to study law at the Law school of Beirut, where he was converted to Christianity, perhaps under the influence of his biographer. He was baptised in 488 at the shrine of Saint Leontius in Tripoli. He became a monk and resided in a monastery near Gaza - a stronghold of Monophysites. When Flavian II was deposed from the patriarchal see of Antioch in 512, Severus was elected as his successor. However, with the death of the emperor Anastasius in 518 and because of the pro-Chalcedonian ecclesiastical policy that Anastasius's successor, Justin I, adopted, Severus was forced to leave Antioch. He went to Egypt where he spent the rest of his life until his death, in February of 538. In 536 Justin I had his writings, originally written in Greek, condemned. Therefore, most of them survive only in Syriac translations (theological treatises refuting either Chalcedonian polemic or the more extreme anti-Chalcedonians, an extensive polemical work against Julian of Halicarnassus, as well as a small proportion of his vast correspondence). The hundred-page biography of the Monophysite Patriarch of Antioch was prepared sometime after Severus's accession to the patriarchal throne of Antioch in November 512. It focuses on Severus's career up to his enthronement, without dealing with the events after his accession. Zacharias's intention is to defend his close friend and fellow student against rumors that claimed that Severus was a devout pagan during his student years in Alexandria, while he participated and offered sacrifices while studying in Beirut. The "Life" consists of four sections: it begins with a short dialogue between Zacharias and an anonymous person, where the author of the text becomes aware of the slanders against Severus. Next, Zacharias focuses on the early years of Severus's life, his family background and his rhetorical training in Alexandria, describing the experiences of Severus as a member of a group of Alexandrian "philoponoi", that is, Christian zealots students like Zacharias, who had close ties to the monophysite monastic community of "Enaton", near Alexandria. Apart from the facts, however, that describe Severus's life, what is also quite significant with the text is the fact that it provides us with first-hand information about the student life in Alexandria and Beirut and the conflicts between pagans and Christians and the anti-pagan policy of Emperor Zeno. Zacharias interposes the case of Paralius, a pagan student who was converted to Christianity. Because Paralius accused his teacher, Horapollo the Younger, and his circle of sorcery and witchcraft, he was beaten up by his fellow students. Because of that, a series of anti-pagan riots broke out in Alexandria, guided by the Patriarch Peter III Mongus, which led to the looting of the sanctuary of Isis in Menouthis and the burning of pagan cult objects. Shortly after, Emperor Zeno sent delegates to Alexandria to investigate whether the pagan teachers practiced pagan rituals. The result was the ill-treatment and expulsion of prominent pagan (mostly neoplatonic) teachers. After Paralius's incident, Zacharias takes his readers to Beirut, where he describes Severus's legal studies. There, Severus participates in a group of zealot Christian students in close contact with monophysite monastic centers in Palestine. Severus provides religious instruction to his fellow students, while he fights paganism in the student community of the city, organizing raids. The final section of the text emphasizes on Severus's decision to abandon his legal career and retire to a monastery near the town of Maiuma in Gaza.

Date Range: 512 CE - 518 CE

Region: Antioch, Syria

Region tags: Syria, Antioch

Antioch was the third largest city within the Roman Empire in the 1st century CE. It was a major center of Second Temple Judaism and a foundational center for early Christianity as well.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: AMBJÖRN, LENA. “The Life of Severus” by Zachariah of Mytilene. Piscataway NJ: Gorgias Press, 2008.
- Source 2: Sévère, Patriarche d'Antioche, 512-518 / textes syriaques publiés, traduits et annotés par M.-A. Kugener.
- Source 3: The Life of Severus in French (Patrologia Orientalis vol. 2), Brepols, 1902

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://gedsh.bethmardutho.org/Severus-of-Antioch>
- Source 1 Description: Severus of Antioch (d. 538)
- Source 2 URL: <https://syri.ac/authorsa-ja/severus-antioch?page=5>
- Source 2 Description: SEVERUS OF ANTIOCH

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: https://www.tertullian.org/rpearse/pdf.articles/Zacharias_Rhetor_Life_Of_Severus_1_122.pdf
- Source 1 Description: The Life of Severus in French (Patrologia Orientalis)
- Source 2 URL: <https://hal.science/hal-03317907/document>
- Source 2 Description: Les scholastiques dans la correspondance patriarcale de Sévère d'Antioche (512-518), by Frédéric Alpi

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked
–with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

–Other textile: parchment

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Materiality

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Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: On the contrary, because of the fact that Zacharias, its author, was a member of the monophysite party, the original text in Greek language was destroyed.

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

- ↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for religious professionals?
– No
- ↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for all adherents?
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- ↳ Is proselytizing or missionary work part of the historical culture of the community referenced in the text?
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- ↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?
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- ↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
– No
- ↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
– No
- ↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
– No
- ↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: It should be noted however that Severus is considered as a saint of the Coptic Church. His life therefore is important in Coptic hagiography.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None of the above.

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts
– No

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities
– Yes

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)
– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)
– All individuals within society

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Zacharias reports the case of Asklepiodotos, a pagan senate in the city of Aphrodisias, who desired to have children but his wife was sterile. According to Zacharias, God inflicted on him as a punishment, because he dealt with the evil practices of magic, the deprivation of children and the sterility of his wife.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god
– Yes

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means
 - No
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
- ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

Notes: Zacharias reports that when the imposture of Asklepiodotus was known to everyone, the bishop of Alexandria, Peter Mongus, addressed a synodal letter to the bishop of Aphrodisias, in which he described all the machinations of the pagans. This letter was not delivered, since the person who had been charged with carrying it had been, on his arrival in Caria, corrupted by a gift. However, another senate named Adrastus, a pious man according to Zacharias, took action against Asklepiodotus.

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: Not exactly. The original, in Greek language, text is lost, being a victim of the anti-monophysite policies. However, the translation of the text in Syriac is extant.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: However, the life of Severus could be considered as part of a "Monophysitic trilogy". The author of the text, Zachariah Scholasticus, also wrote the "Life of Peter the Iberian" and the "Life of Abbah Isaiah". All three of them were prominent monophysite leaders.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Cooperation
– No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Field doesn't know

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– No

↳ Other important virtues
– Field doesn't know

Does the text require fasting?
– Yes

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?
– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?
– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?
– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?
– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?
– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?
– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?
– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god
– Specify: Benevolent, benign, merciful.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– No

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– No

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Field doesn't know

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No

↳ Can be hurt?
– No

↳ Can be tricked?
– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
– Specify: No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?
– No

Previously human spirits are present
– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?
– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: The text refers to various ways of communication with the supernatural beings. However, none of these efforts is successful, since pagan deities or beings belonging to the pagan pantheon are considered to be fake and futile.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: According to the text, the pagans believed that the supernatural beings of their religion possessed powers, however their powers never manifest in the world

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: Zacharias uses the generic term "demons" to refer to the pagan deities. These latter come from the Egyptian as well as the Greek pantheon.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: Zacharias, however, refers (albeit implicitly) to formulas for invoking the gods of the pagans. He mentions a kind of paper (or map) with incantations through which pagans invoked their gods.

Furthermore, Zacharias refers to the sacrifices that the pagans offered in Caria, dissecting livers and

examining them by magic, in order to learn whether Leontios, Illos and Pamprepios would defeat Emperor Zeno. These latter had rebelled against the Emperor in order to re-establish paganism. They actually received a multitude of oracles along with promises that Emperor Zeno could not withstand their shock and that Christianity would fall apart and disappear. Eventually the rebellion failed.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?
– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?
– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: Not exactly. The original, in Greek language, text is lost, being a victim of the anti-monophysite policies. However, the translation of the text in Syriac is extant.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

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Notes: However, the life of Severus could be considered as part of a "Monophysitic trilogy". The author of the text, Zachariah Scholasticus, also wrote the "Life of Peter the Iberian" and the "Life of Abbah Isaiah". All three of them were prominent monophysite leaders.

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Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None of the above.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

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Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

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Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

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Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

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Are formal burials present in the text?

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Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

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Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Zacharias uses the generic term "demons" to refer to the pagan deities. These latter come from the Egyptian as well as the Greek pantheon.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: Zacharias, however, refers (albeit implicitly) to formulas for invoking the gods of the pagans. He mentions a kind of paper (or map) with incantations through which pagans invoked their gods. Furthermore, Zacharias refers to the sacrifices that the pagans offered in Caria, dissecting livers and examining them by magic, in order to learn whether Leontios, Illos and Pamprepios would defeat Emperor Zeno. These latter had rebelled against the Emperor in order to re-establish paganism. They actually received a multitude of oracles along with promises that Emperor Zeno could not withstand their shock and that Christianity would fall apart and disappear. Eventually the rebellion failed.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Zacharias reports the case of Asklepiodotos, a pagan senate in the city of Aphrodisias, who desired to have children but his wife was sterile. According to Zacharias, God inflicted on him as a punishment, because he dealt with the evil practices of magic, the deprivation of children and the sterility of his wife.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

Notes: Zacharias reports that when the imposture of Asklepiodotus was known to everyone, the bishop of Alexandria, Peter Mongus, addressed a synodal letter to the bishop of Aphrodisias, in which he described all the machinations of the pagans. This letter was not delivered, since the person who had been charged with carrying it had been, on his arrival in Caria, corrupted by a gift. However, another senate named Adrastus, a pious man according to Zacharias, took action against Asklepiodotus.

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts
– No

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities
– Yes

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)
– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)
– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)
– No

↳ Courage (generic)
– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes

- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Field doesn't know

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– No

↳ Other important virtues
– Field doesn't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?
– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?
– No

Does the text require castration?
– No

Does the text require fasting?
– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?
– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?
– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?
– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: Not exactly. The author of the text refers quite often to violent conflicts between pagans and Christians in both Alexandria and Beirut. Zacharias, for example, reports a raid at a house in Menouthis, which was completely covered with pagan inscriptions (hieroglyphics). In one of its corners was built a double wall. Behind this wall were hidden the idols. A narrow entrance in the form of a window led to it, and it was through this that the priest entered to perform the sacrifices. Wanting the search to lead to nothing, the pagans had blocked the entrance with stones. Moreover, so that we do not notice the recent character of the masonry and so that we do not discover the ruse and the artifice, they had placed in front of this place a piece of furniture filled with incense and they had hung a lamp over it, which

burned while it was broad daylight. They opened with an axe what had been freshly built and saw the multitude of idols, the altar covered in blood. These idols were said to have been removed from the temple that Isis once had at Memphis by the priest of that time, when it was found that paganism had lost its strength, and was abolished. We delivered to the flames those of the idols which, because of their great antiquity, were already in large part deteriorated.

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: The text was translated in Syriac language and disseminated by the monophysite party.

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The monophysite party.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: Due to the imperial policy, the original text in Greek language was destroyed.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Field doesn't know

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– Field doesn't know

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: The text was translated in Syriac language and disseminated by the monophysite party.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The monophysite party.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: Due to the imperial policy, the original text in Greek language was destroyed.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

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Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

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Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: Not exactly. The author of the text refers quite often to violent conflicts between pagans and

Christians in both Alexandria and Beirut. Zacharias, for example, reports a raid at a house in Menouthis, which was completely covered with pagan inscriptions (hieroglyphics). In one of its corners was built a double wall. Behind this wall were hidden the idols. A narrow entrance in the form of a window led to it, and it was through this that the priest entered to perform the sacrifices. Wanting the search to lead to nothing, the pagans had blocked the entrance with stones. Moreover, so that we do not notice the recent character of the masonry and so that we do not discover the ruse and the artifice, they had placed in front of this place a piece of furniture filled with incense and they had hung a lamp over it, which burned while it was broad daylight. They opened with an axe what had been freshly built and saw the multitude of idols, the altar covered in blood. These idols were said to have been removed from the temple that Isis once had at Memphis by the priest of that time, when it was found that paganism had lost its strength, and was abolished. We delivered to the flames those of the idols which, because of their great antiquity, were already in large part deteriorated.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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